

Performance Comparison of kNN and GD

Data Collection

What data will you collect or create?

Input Data

In this experiment two external datasets will be used: fish and employee.

The fish dataset is from kaggle.com.

In the following paragraph the data this project uses and collects are described:

The employee dataset is from openml.org and provides annual salary information including gross pay and overtime pay for all active, permanent employees of Montgomery County, MD paid in calendar year 2016. It is composed of 13 features and 9222 rows of data. The data is published under the Public Domain (CC0) and was last updated 2019-09-12. It is accessible in the ARFF format. This format describes its data as a list of instances sharing a set of attributes. It is an ASCII text file that is human readable and parsable by many ARFF parsers implemented in different programming languages, for this experiment we will use liac-arff for python.

Link to Page: <https://www.openml.org/d/42125>

Link to ARFF: <https://www.openml.org/data/download/21718841/dataset>

Save the file to: evaluation/fish/data/fish.csv

The fish dataset is from kaggle.com and provides records of 7 common different fish species in fish market sales. It is published under the GNU General Public License, version 2 and was created and last updated in 2019-06-13. We will use Version 2 of the fish dataset provided by SAS Ondemand for Academics. The file consists of 7 columns and has 159 rows of data. CSV is a widely used format to store data in a human readable format and its format is used.

Link to Page: <https://www.kaggle.com/aungpyaeap/fish-market>

Save the file to: evaluation/employee/data/employee.arff

Produced Data

Right before evaluation, each dataset will be split into two parts (learn and test set) of variable size in CSV format. The employee dataset is converted to CSV before this step resulting in following new files:

- fish.lrn.csv
File size: 17 KB
- fish.tes.csv
File size: 2 KB
- employee.csv
File size: 1 506 KB
- employee.lrn.csv
File size: 1 247 KB
- employee.tes.csv
File size: 139 KB

CSV are used as they are very well integrated into the python / numpy / sklearn ecosystem and are human readable.

For each dataset there will be created two new CSV files which contain metrics data in CSV format. There will be two files of 36 rows with 7 columns, two files of 64 rows with 7

columns each and four plots are created as PNG. PNG is used as it is the most used lossless compression image format and is recommended by the W3C.

- gd_fish.csv
File size: 3 KB
 - knn_fish.csv
File size: 5 KB
 - gd_fish_scatterplot.png
File size: 301 KB
Dimensions: 2560 x 1920 pixels
 - knn_fish_scatterplot.png
File size: 218 KB
Dimensions: 2560 x 1920 pixels
-
- gd_employee.csv
File size: 2,57 Bytes
 - knn_employee.csv
File size: 5,44 KB
 - gd_fish_scatterplot.png
File size: 794 KB
Dimensions: 2560 x 1920 pixels
 - knn_fish_scatterplot.png
File size: 723 KB
Dimensions: 2560 x 1920 pixels

In a second step 36 new plots are produced again in PNG format with 3840 x 2880 pixels resulting in 7,76 MB of data. These files are not important to store long term as they can be easily be recreated. with the files above.

- gd_employee_0.0001_mae.png
- gd_employee_0.0001_mse.png
- gd_employee_0.0001_r2.png
- gd_employee_0.001_mae.png
- gd_employee_0.001_mse.png
- gd_employee_0.001_r2.png
- gd_employee_0.01_mae.png
- gd_employee_0.01_mse.png
- gd_employee_0.01_r2.png
- gd_employee_performance.png
- gd_fish_0.0001_mae.png
- gd_fish_0.0001_mse.png
- gd_fish_0.0001_r2.png
- gd_fish_0.001_mae.png
- gd_fish_0.001_mse.png
- gd_fish_0.001_r2.png
- gd_fish_0.01_mae.png
- gd_fish_0.01_mse.png
- gd_fish_0.01_r2.png
- gd_fish_performance.png
- knn_employee_euclidean_mae.png
- knn_employee_euclidean_mse.png
- knn_employee_euclidean_r2.png

- knn_employee_manhattan_mae.png
- knn_employee_manhattan_mse.png
- knn_employee_manhattan_r2.png
- knn_employee_performance.png
- knn_fish_euclidean_mae.png
- knn_fish_euclidean_mse.png
- knn_fish_euclidean_r2.png
- knn_fish_manhattan_mae.png
- knn_fish_manhattan_mse.png
- knn_fish_manhattan_r2.png
- knn_fish_performance.png

How will the data be collected or created?

The following data formats are used in this project:

- ARFF
- CSV
- PNG

While we tried to minimize the different used formats in this project, we could not further reduce the amount of formats while keeping the code and structure of the project as simple as possible.

The ARFF format is needed as one of the external datasets is only available in this dataset. The ARFF file will be converted into CSV format automatically to make the further process more consistent and the file easier to read.

The CSV format is our go to format for our created data as it is very easy to handle and is deeply integrated into most programming languages, operating systems and environments.

The project is split into three main folders: algorithms, evaluation and plotting. In the algorithms folder are the implementations of the algorithms that are compared against the state of the art implementation of skelarn. In the evaluation folder there are two folders for the external datasets: fish and employee. Each of these folders is structured exactly the same, there are the folders data (here will the external data set go) and results (here will the produced results be). Next to these two folders, there is an executable python file named "predictor.py" .

The structure of the project can be visualized by the list below:

- algorithms
 - gd
 - knn
- evaluation
 - employee
 - data
 - results
 - fish

- data
 - results
- plotting
 - evaluations
 - plots

The external data set files (ARFF and CSV) should be moved into the data appropriate folder and be named exactly as the folder and its format it is in. So the fish dataset should be in the fish/data folder named fish.csv.

Right before evaluation, each dataset will be split into two parts (learn and test set) of variable size. These files contain a subset of the original dataset, combined yielding the full dataset. The employee dataset will first be converted into a CSV file automatically. The resulting files look like:

- evaluation/fish/data/fish.lrn.csv
- evaluation/fish/data/fish.tes.csv
- evaluation/employee/data/employee.csv
- evaluation/employee/data/employee.lrn.csv
- evaluation/employee/data/employee.tes.csv

For each data set the lrn and tes variant we will be used to evaluate the newly implemented algorithms as well as for the state of the art implementation in sklearn. This process produces a variety of new data. For each dataset there will be created two new CSV files which contain metrics data in CSV format. There will be two files of 36 rows with 7 columns and two files of 64 rows with 7 columns each:

- evaluation/fish/result/knn_fish.csv
- evaluation/fish/result/gd_fish.csv
- evaluation/employee/result/knn_employee.csv
- evaluation/employee/result/gd_employee.csv

Furthermore, four plots are created while evaluating the algorithms on the external datasets:

- evaluation/fish/result/knn_fish_scatterplot.png
- evaluation/fish/result/gd_fish_scatterplot.png
- evaluation/employee/result/knn_employee_scatterplot.png
- evaluation/employee/result/gd_employee_scatterplot.png

The plots are saved as PNG files with about 250kB each.

The generated csv files in the results folder can be used to create 36 additional plots over the data. Therefore the data has to be copied or moved to the plotting/evaluations folder, keeping the original naming!

With the runnable python file in the plotting folder, 36 new plots are saved to the plotting/plots folder. 32 of the plots show specific metrics and follow the naming convention:

{algorithm}_{dataset}_{value of altered variable}_{metric}.png

The other 4 plots are performance plots and are named:

{algorithm}_{dataset}_performance.png

Versioning

To track changes of data, code and structure, git will be used. The project is available under <https://github.com/kooperativ97/THRegressor>

Quality Assurance

There are no quality assurance measures planned for this project but the tracking over

git.

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

Metadata to the data sets will be available in github, where it will be shortly described in the README and information is given on how and where to download the files.

The produced data will also be shortly described in the README file of the project, useful links are given to understand the retrieved data so that people who like to reuse the data can have a basic understanding. All columns will be shortly mentioned with a short description and what values to expect. As this documentation is on the GitHub repository, it can be accessed with the code and data in the repository.

There is no metadata provided for the datasets by the publishers but boxplots of value distribution and information about missing values. These informations can be found at the links for the data sets fish: <https://www.kaggle.com/aungpyaeap/fish-market> and employee: <https://www.openml.org/d/42125>.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage any ethical issues?

Fish Dataset

The fish dataset does not contain any sensitive or personal information as it is just made of measurements of different fish.

Employee

The employee dataset contains personal information like names, salary and gender, but as these employee data is publicly available by law and was published under CC0, I will not take any measure to anonymize the data.

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

Input Data

The employee data used is published under Creative Commons 0 into the Public Domain, so there is no problem with copyright infringement.

The fish data used is published under GNU General Public License, version 2.

Output Data

The produced output data will be published under GNU General Public License, version 2 free to copy and modify by anyone else as long as the changes get tracked accordingly.

Code

The code will be published under GNU General Public License, version 3 which allows others to reuse, modify and distribute this project in any form , except a closed source one.

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

During development the data is backed up on a private git server on git.overheat.me where the code and data sets are hosted in a private repository which is only accessible to Tobias Hajszan and Moritz Staudinger. Only with the right SSH key, data can be seen and manipulated. All changes are logged with git automatically.

After completing the development the data and source code is backed up in GitHub in the Performance Comparison of kNN and GD repository (available under: <https://github.com/kooperativ97/Performance-Comparison-of-kNN-and-GD>) . Every release will be uploaded into the Microsoft OneDrive Cloud Service as a zipped package in ZIP format named after the commit identifier and is published on Zenodo as well.

The complete repository is furthermore saved on a local Qnap NAS Device (RAID 5) and will be updated with every new commit as a zipped package in ZIP format by one of the project members.

How will you manage access and security?

As this project is hosted as a repository on GitHub, only members of the repository are able to create, modify or delete data in the project. Access is only given to project participants, so Moritz Staudinger and Tobias Hajszan.

The github project is linked to the account kooperativ69 which is secured via password and two-factor authentication.

Selection and Preservation

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

The CSV files used for the experiment and the generated CSV files from the program should be kept safe so the experiment can easily be redone. As a random state is given in the program, every run should yield the same result, given the input does not change. Therefore, the most important data to be preserved are the two external datasets:

- evaluation/fish/data/fish.csv
- evaluation/employee/data/employee.arff

These will be committed with the git repository as they are of very small size: 1,5 MB for the employee dataset and 6 KB for the fish dataset. The data and the code will stay in the GitHub-Repository until December 31st 2021.

The data set files fish.csv and employee.arff will be published on Zenodo as well with a unique identifier.

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

The dataset will be published on Zenodo, the source code and documentation to GitHub. Both services are free of charge as of 18.04.2021. As long as this service is free of charge, it is planned to keep all data sets and source code on Zenodo and GitHub. There is no plans on migrating the data onto other platforms or services in the future.

Data Sharing

How will you share the data?

The data will be published on Zenodo, the source code on GitHub. All data is shared under Creative Commons Attribution 1.0 Generic (CC-BY). The code is shared under GNU General Public License, version 3 which allows others to reuse, modify and distribute this project in any form , except a closed source one.

An embargo period is set onto the data on Zenodo to the April 19th 2021.

The source code will be available on April 18th 2021.

Source code and data sets will be given a unique digital identifier.

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

No, there are no restrictions on the data or source code.

Responsibilities and Resources

Who will be responsible for data management?

Tobias Hajszan is responsible for implementing the DMP and reviewing and revising this plan when changes are made to the project. Tobias Hajszan is reachable under tobias.hajszan@outlook.com.

As the project will not be further developed there should not be a need of changing source code or data.

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

No resources are required to deliver this plan.